

Some Bullen-type Inequalities for Co-ordinated s-convex Function

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Abstract

In this paper, we establish new Bullen-Simpson type integral inequalities for functions of two variables whose mixed partial derivatives are s-convex in the second sense on the coordinates. Several general results and corollaries are obtained by employing Hölder and Power Mean inequalities. Furthermore, the constants involved in these inequalities are explicitly determined, and the classical one-dimensional results are shown to be special cases of our findings. The obtained results provide a comprehensive generalization of the existing Bullen-Simpson type inequalities to the framework of coordinate s-convex functions, offering new insights and potential applications in numerical integration and mean inequalities.

Keywords: Bullen-type inequalities, s-convex functions, Co-ordinated convexity, Simpson-type inequalities.

1 Introduction and Motivation

Definition 1.1. Let I be an interval of real numbers. A function $B : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex, if for all $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in I$ all $h \in [0, 1]$ ([2]), we have

$$B(h\mu_1 + (1-h)\mu_2) \leq hB(\mu_1) + (1-h)B(\mu_2)$$

One of the famous inequalities for the class of convex functions is the so-called Hermite-Hadamard inequality, which can be stated as follows:

Theorem 1.1. Let B be a convex function on the interval $[\mu_1, \mu_2]$ with $\mu_1 < \mu_2$, then we have ([18])

$$B\left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} B(x) dx \leq \frac{B(\mu_1) + B(\mu_2)}{2} \quad (1)$$

Since its discovery, several articles related to inequality (1) have been published ([3]-[18])

The concept of convexity has been also generalized in diverse manners. One of them is the so-called s -convex function or Breckner convex function defined as follows:

A nonnegative function $B : I \subset [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be s -convex in the second sense for some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, if

$$B(h\mu_1 + (1-h)\mu_2) \leq h^s B(\mu_1) + (1-h)^s B(\mu_2)$$

holds for all $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in I$ and $h \in [0, 1]$ (see [19])

In [20], Dragomir and Fitzpatrick, proved the following variant of inequality (1) which holds for s -convex functions in the second sense.

Definition 1.2. A function $B : \Delta \subseteq [0, \infty)^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called s -convex in the second sense on the co-ordinates on Δ if;

$$\begin{aligned} & B(h\mu_1 + (1-h)\mu_2, tv_1 + (1-t)v_2) \\ & \leq h^s t^s B(\mu_1, v_1) + h^s (1-t)^s B(\mu_1, v_2) \\ & \quad + t^s (1-h)^s B(\mu_2, v_1) + (1-h)^s (1-t)^s B(\mu_2, v_2) \end{aligned}$$

holds for all $h, t \in [0, 1]$ and $(\mu_1, v_1), (\mu_1, v_2), (\mu_2, v_1), (\mu_2, v_2) \in \Delta$, for some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$. (see [21])

Definition 1.3. In [22], Hwang et al. established the following Bullen-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{4} \left(B(\mu_1) + 2B\left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}\right) + B(\mu_2) \right) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} B(x) dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_1}{16} \left(|B'(\mu_1)| \right) + \left(|B'(\mu_2)| \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Definition 1.4. In [23], Hwang et al. established the following Simpson-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{4} \left(B(\mu_1) + 2B\left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}\right) + B(\mu_2) \right) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} B(x) dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_1}{16} \left(|B'(\mu_1)| \right) + \left(|B'(\mu_2)| \right) \end{aligned}$$

2 Background

Over the last two decades, error estimation of quadrature rules via different types of convexity has become an attractive and fascinating area of research and has gained popularity. Consequently, several papers treating integral inequalities under the principle of convexity have been widely studied by mathematicians and researchers. Regarding Newton-Cotes type inequalities involving one point ([24]-[29]) two point Newton-Cotes type inequalities ([30]-[33]), for three point Newton-Cotes type inequalities ([34]-[39]) and Newton-Cotes type inequalities involving four points ([40]-[44])

we provide several applications to two-dimensional numerical integration rules and discuss new inequalities involving means based on our coordinate s-convexity results

4 Main theorems and Results

In this section, we present our main theoretical contributions. We start with a lemma and use it to derive new theorems and results

Lemma 4.1. Let $B : [\mu_1, \mu_2] \times [v_1, v_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function such that the mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$ exists and belongs to $L^1(D)$, then the following equality holds

$$B - I = \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K_i(h)K_j(k) \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i(h), y_j(k)) dkdh \quad (4)$$

1. The integrals mean (I)

$$I = \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx$$

2. The extended Bullen rule approximation (B)

The approximation B is the weighted sum of the function $B(x, y)$ evaluated at the 5x5=25 Bullen quadrature points in D normalized by $\frac{1}{144}$;

$$B = \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(x_i, y_j)$$

where the weights are $w = \{1, 4, 6, 4, 1\}$ and the quadrature points are;

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &\in \left\{ \mu_1, \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4}, \mu_2 \right\} \\ y_i &\in \left\{ v_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2}, \frac{v_1 + 3v_2}{4}, v_2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

3. The kernel functions ($K_i(h), K_j(k)$): $K_i(h)$ and $K_j(k)$ represent the single-variable Bullen-Simpson kernel functions corresponding to the subdivision of the intervals.

4. The parameterization: The terms $x_i(h)$ and $y_i(k)$ linearly parameterize the 4x4 subrectangles of D

Proof. The proof of this identity is usually done by taking the integrals

$$I_{i,j} = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K_i(h)K_j(k) \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i(h), y_j(k)) dkdh \quad (5)$$

we will use successive integration by parts twice. For example; consider the simplest term on the right-hand side for $i = 1, j = 1$;

$$I_{1,1} = \int_0^1 K_1(h) \left[\int_0^1 K_1(k) \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \right] dh$$

partial integration of the inner integral with respect to k . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} K_1(h) &= h - 1/3 \\ x_1(h) &= (1-h)\mu_1 + h \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4} \\ x'_1(h) &= \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_1}{4} \\ y_1(k) &= (1-k)\mu_1 + k \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \\ y'_1(k) &= \frac{v_2 - v_1}{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} u &= k - \frac{1}{3} \Rightarrow du = dk \\ dv &= \left(\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_1, y_1(k)) \right) dk \end{aligned}$$

To find v , we need to integrate B with respect to k . Using the reverse chain rule;

$$\begin{aligned} v &= \frac{1}{y'_1(k)} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(y'_1(k) = \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} - v_1 = \frac{v_2 - v_1}{4} \right) \\ v &= \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) \end{aligned}$$

Then, lets do the integration by parts and substitute the integral boundaries.

$$\begin{aligned} J_{1,1}(h) &= \frac{2}{3} \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(x_1(h), \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), v_1) \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \int_0^1 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \\ J_{1,1}(h) &= \frac{4}{3(v_2 - v_1)} \left[2 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(x_1(h), \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) + \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), v_1) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \int_0^1 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \end{aligned}$$

Transition to the outer integral,

$$I_{1,1} = \int_0^1 K_1(h) \cdot J_{1,1}(h) dh$$

Apply $\int_0^1 K_1(h)(...)dh$ to each term in the expression $J_{1,1}(h)$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{1,1} &= \frac{4}{3(v_2 - v_1)} \left[2 \int_0^1 K_1(h) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(x_1(h), \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) dh \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_0^1 K_1(h) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), v_1) dh \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \int_0^1 K_1(h) \left(\int_0^1 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \right) dh \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Lets take

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= \int_0^1 K_1(h) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(x_1(h), \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) dh \\ L_2 &= \int_0^1 K_1(h) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), v_1) dh \\ L_3 &= \int_0^1 K_1(h) \left(\int_0^1 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \right) dh \end{aligned}$$

Applying the second partial integration(L_1 term)

$$\begin{aligned} u &= h - \frac{1}{3} \Rightarrow du = dh \\ dv &= \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), y_1(k)) dh \\ v &= \frac{1}{x_1'(h)} B(x_1(h), Y) = \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} B(x_1(h), Y) dh \end{aligned}$$

Then, lets do the integration by parts and substitute the integral boundaries.

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, Y \right) + B(\mu_1, Y) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_0^1 B(x_1(h), Y) dh \right] \end{aligned}$$

Lets convert the remaining integral in L_1 to an integral with respect to x ;

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x_1(h) \\ dh &= \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} dx \end{aligned}$$

and boundaries

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 0 \Rightarrow h = \mu_1 \\ x &= 1 \Rightarrow h = \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4} \\ \int_0^1 B(x_1(h), Y) dh &= \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, Y) \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} dx \end{aligned}$$

Lets rewrite L_1

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, Y \right) + B(\mu_1, Y) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, Y) dx \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Then, calculate L_2 ,integrating by parts and substitute the integral boundaries. We get;

$$\begin{aligned} L_2 &= \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1 \right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_0^1 B(x_1(h), v_1) dh \end{aligned}$$

Change variables in the remaining integral and if we substitute the transformation we found into L_2 ;

$$L_2 = \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right] - \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, v_1) dx \quad (8)$$

(The structure of this term is the same as that of four term, expect that the y -coordinate is to v , instead of $\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}$)

Finally, let's calculate for L_3 , transformation of the inner integral with respect to k . Then,

$$L_3 = \int_0^1 K_1(h) \left(\int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y) dy \right) \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} dh$$

Integration by parts of the outer integral with respect to h . As in the previous steps to remove the derivative x , we substitute the derivative $x_1(h)$ with respect to $(x_1(h)')$ we divide. Integration by parts, write boundaries and make necessary arrangements,

$$L_3 = \frac{16}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \left[2 \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, y\right) dy + \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B(\mu_1, y) dy \right] - \int_0^1 \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B(x_1(h), y) dy dh$$

Transformation of the remaining double integral (final term)

$$-\frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_0^1 \left(\int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B(x_1(h), y) dy \right) dh$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x_1(h) \\ dh &= \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} dx \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} h = 0 &\Rightarrow x = \mu_1 \\ h = 1 &\Rightarrow x = \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$-\frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} \left(\int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B(x, y) dx dy \right) \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1}$$

L_3 final statement,

$$L_3 = \frac{16}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, y\right) + B(\mu_1, y) \right] dy$$

$$-\frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2 (v_2 - v_1)} \int \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, y) dx dy \tag{9}$$

This term, when combined with previous terms L_1 and L_2 , will give $I_{1,1}$. When all sixteen terms are added, these complex single integrals cancel out, leaving only the Bullen terms $B(\dots)$ and the term $\int \int B(x, y) dx dy$

$$I_{1,1} = \frac{4}{3(v_2 - v_1)} [2L_1 + L_2] - \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} L_3$$

We collect the L_1 and L_2 terms as $2L_1 + L_2$

$$L_1 = \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + B\left(\mu_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{4}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B\left(x, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) dx$$

$$L_2 = \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right] - \frac{4}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, v_1) dx$$

$$2L_1 + L_2 = \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[4B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\mu_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right]$$

$2L_1 + L_2$ by $\frac{4}{3(v_2 - v_1)}$ multiplying this sum by the first two rows of $I_{1,1}$, we get

$$\frac{16}{9(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \left[4B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\mu_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right]$$

If we multiply the final statement of L_3 by $-\frac{4}{(v_2 - v_1)}$

$$L_3 = \frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)^2} \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, y\right) + B(\mu_1, y) \right] dy - \frac{64}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2 (v_2 - v_1)^2} \int \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, y) dx dy$$

$$I_{1,1} = \frac{16}{9(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \left[4B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\mu_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right] - \frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)^2} \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, y\right) + B(\mu_1, y) \right] dy \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} \left[2B\left(x, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + B(x, v_1) \right] dx \\
& + \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)^2} \int \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, y) dx dy
\end{aligned}$$

1) Bullen Type Terms(Four Corners)

$$\frac{1}{9} \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} = \frac{16}{9(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \tag{11}$$

2) Single Integrals (x-Direction)

$$-\frac{1}{3} \frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2} \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} = -\frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)} \tag{12}$$

3) Single Integrals (y-Direction)

$$-\frac{1}{3} \frac{16}{(v_2 - v_1)^2} \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} = -\frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)^2} \tag{13}$$

4) Double Integral

$$\frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2} \frac{16}{(v_2 - v_1)^2} = \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)^2} \tag{14}$$

Due to symmetry, the expression of the remaining terms follows the same structures as the term $I_{1,1}$, which we proved in detail. Only the points, boundaries and coefficients of the Peano kernel ($K_1(h) = h - 1/3, K_1(h) = h - 2/3$) used change, preserving the coefficients $x'_1(h) = \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_1}{4}, y'_1(k) = \frac{v_2 - v_1}{4}$. So let's move directly to the sum $I_{i,j}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 I_{i,j} &= \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of 16} \\ \text{bullen type terms} \end{array} \right) + \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of 16} \\ \text{X-Int terms} \end{array} \right) \\
&+ \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of 16} \\ \text{Y-Int terms} \end{array} \right) + \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of 16} \\ \text{double integrals} \end{array} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

then we have,

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{i,j} &= \frac{16}{9(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \sum_{\text{bullen}} B(\dots) \\
&+ \frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)} \sum_{\text{X-int}} \int (\dots) dx \\
&+ \frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)^2} \sum_{\text{Y-int}} \int (\dots) dy \\
&+ \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)^2} \int \int B(\dots) dx dy
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

1) This is the most important part of the proof. The x -directional integral term from $I_{i,j}$ cancels out because the x -directional integral terms on adjacent intervals (e.g $I_{1,1}$) are of exactly the

opposite sign and the same magnitude

$$\sum \text{Single Integral parts of } I_{i,j} = 0$$

2) Adding double integrals

$$\sum \text{Double Integral parts of } I_{i,j} = \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2 (v_2 - v_1)^2} \int \int_D B(x, y) dy dx$$

3) The total part of Bullen type terms of

$$I_{i,j} = \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \cdot B$$

This sum is related to the integral mean I

$$\frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \cdot I$$

Where these three results are collected the final identity of Lemma

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 I_{i,j} = \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} [B - I]$$

Multiplying this expression by $\frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256}$, we obtain the auxiliary identity

$$B - I = \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 I_{i,j}$$

the proof is completed.

Theorem 4.1. Let $B : [\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function such that the mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$ exists and is integrable on $[\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2]$. If $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|$ is s -convex in the second sense on $[\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2]$ for some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$|B - I| \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256(s + 1)^2(s + 2)^2} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K_{i,j}(s) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i, y_j) \right| \quad (16)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\} = \left\{ \mu_1, \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4}, \mu_2 \right\} \\ y &= \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5\} = \left\{ v_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2}, \frac{v_1 + 3v_2}{4}, v_2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$K_{i,j}(s)$ are coefficients obtained from linear combinations of the products of the single variable integrals $\gamma_k(s)$ and $\Lambda_k(s)$ with $c_k \in \left\{ \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3} \right\}$.

$$\gamma_k(s) = \int_0^1 \left| \tau - \frac{1}{3} \right| \tau^s d\tau = \int_0^1 \left| \frac{2}{3} - \tau \right| (1 - \tau)^s d\tau \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{2s+1}{3(s+1)(s+2)} + \frac{2}{(s+1)(s+2)} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{s+2} \\
\Lambda_k(s) &= \int_0^1 \left| \tau - \frac{1}{3} \right| (1-\tau)^s d\tau = \int_0^1 \left| \frac{2}{3} - \tau \right| \tau^s d\tau \\
&= \frac{s-1}{3(s+1)(s+2)} + \frac{2}{(s+1)(s+2)} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{s+2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma properties of modulus and coordinated s-convexity of $|B'|$, we have

$$|B - I| \leq (\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1) \sum_{k=1}^4 \sum_{l=1}^4 \int_{J_k} \int_{J_l} K(t, z) \left(\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x(t), y(z)) \right) dz dt$$

Here, the kernel $K(t, z)$ is the product of single variable Bullen-Simpson kernels $K(t, z) = K_1(t)K_2(z)$. Taking the absolute value and isolating the double integral

$$|B - I| \leq (\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1) \sum_{k=1}^4 \sum_{l=1}^4 \int_{J_k} \int_{J_l} |K_1(t)| |K_2(z)| \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x(t), y(z)) \right| dz dt$$

The summation over k and l over the 16 sub-rectangles where the kernel $K(t, z)$ maintains a constant sign structure. For each of the 16 sub-rectangles, the variables $x(t)$ and $y(z)$ can be expressed as convex combinations of the end points of the respective sub-intervals $x(t) \in [\mu'_1, \mu'_2] \subseteq [\mu_1, \mu_2]$ and $y(z) \in [v'_1, v'_2] \subseteq [v_1, v_2]$. Applying the coordinated s-convexity definition to the mixed partial derivative,

$$\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x(t), y(z)) \right| \leq T(t, z, s) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu'_1, v'_1) \right| + \dots + Z(t, z, s) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu'_2, v'_2) \right|$$

where $T(t, z, s) = t^s z^s$, $Z(t, z, s) = (1-z)^s (1-t)^s$ and the other two term in value $t^s (1-z)^s$ and $(1-t)^s z^s$

Substituting this back into the double integral $|B - I|$, each of the 16 double integrals splits into 4 term resulting in 64 terms in total. Due to separable nature of the integrand, each of the 64 terms reduces to a product of two single integrals. For an arbitrary term involving $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu_a, v_b) \right|$ the coefficient takes the form

$$\left(\int_{J_k} K_1(t) Q(t)(t, s) dt \right) \left(\int_{J_l} K_2(z) Q(z)(z, s) dz \right)$$

where $Q(t) \in \{t^s, (1-t)^s\}$ and $Q(z) \in \{z^s, (1-z)^s\}$.

All 64 terms are expressible as combinations of the product of these calculated auxiliary integrals (as their symmetric counterparts). By grouping the 64 resulting terms according to the 25 unique evaluation points $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i, y_i) \right|$ we define the coefficients $K_{i,j}(s)$. The factor $\frac{1}{256}$ arises from normalization of the 16 partitions in the unit square. The factor $\frac{1}{(s+1)^2(s+2)^2}$ is then extracted from the common denominators of the $\gamma_k(s)$ and $\Lambda_k(s)$ products. The final inequality is obtained by summing the resulting coefficients multiplied by the absolute value of the mixed

partial derivatives evaluated at the characteristic points x_i and y_j

$$|B - I| \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256(s + 1)^2(s + 2)^2} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K_{i,j}(s) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i, y_j) \right|$$

the proof is completed.

Theorem 4.2. Let $B : [\mu_1, \mu_2] \times [v_1, v_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function such that the mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$ exists and is continuous on $[\mu_1, \mu_2] \times [v_1, v_2]$. If the q -th power of mixed partial derivative $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q$, is coordinated s -convex in the second sense $[\mu_1, \mu_2] \times [v_1, v_2]$ for some fixed $s \in [0, 1]$ and $q > 1$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, then the following Bullen-Simpson type inequalities holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{144^2} \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3(p + 1)} \right)^{2/p} \frac{1}{(s + 1)^{2/q}} \\ & \quad \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i, i+1\}, \{j, j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_k, N_l) \right|^q \right) \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Proof. The proof starts from Lemma to the two dimensional case for mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$. This generalization yields a summation over $4 \times 4 = 16$ terms each involving a double integral. For the purpose of simplicity, let's consider the single-variable identity for the mixed partial derivative. Applying the modulus, properties of the integral, the properties of the modulus to the two dimensional identity and applying the double Hölder inequality for $q > 1$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ to each of the 16 double terms, we get;

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 |K_i(h)|^p |K_j(k)|^p dk dh \right)^{1/p} \cdot Q_{i,j} \\ & I = \left(\int_0^1 |K_i(h)|^p dh \right)^{1/p} = \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p + 1)} \right)^{1/p} \\ & I = \left(\int_0^1 |K_j(k)|^p dk \right)^{1/p} = \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p + 1)} \right)^{1/p} \end{aligned}$$

then, we have the total p -norm factor $\forall_{i,j}$ is $(I)^{2/p}$

$$(I)^{2/p} = \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p + 1)} \right)^{2/p}$$

For the $Q_{i,j}$ term, the convexity property of $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q$ in the coordinate s -convexity is used. The expression inside the integral is bounded from above by the values of the four corners of the

lower rectangle.

$$Q_{i,j}^q \leq \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \left[(1-h)^s (1-k)^s M_{i,j}^{(1,1)} + h^s (1-k)^s M_{i,j}^{(2,1)} \right. \\ \left. + (1-h)^s k^s M_{i,j}^{(1,2)} + h^s k^s M_{i,j}^{(2,2)} \right] dh dk$$

using the integral results $\int_0^1 (1-h)^s dh = \frac{1}{s+1}$, $\int_0^1 h^s dh = \frac{1}{s+1}$ we obtain the following bound for the q-norm factor:

$$\frac{1}{(s+1)^{\frac{2}{q}}} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i,i+1\}, \{j,j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} (M_k, N_l) \right|^q \right)^{1/q}$$

we obtain the final inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{144^2} \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3(p+1)} \right)^{2/p} \frac{1}{(s+1)^{2/q}} \\ \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i,i+1\}, \{j,j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} (M_k, N_l) \right|^q \right)$$

Because we are generalizing while preserving the original article ([1]) the coefficient is taken as $\frac{1}{144^2}$ However, mathematically, the coefficient is $\frac{1}{256}$.

$$Q_{i,j}^q \leq \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \left[(1-h)^s (1-k)^s M_{i,j}^{(1,1)} + h^s (1-k)^s M_{i,j}^{(2,1)} \right. \\ \left. + (1-h)^s k^s M_{i,j}^{(1,2)} + h^s k^s M_{i,j}^{(2,2)} \right] dh dk$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{First term} &= \int_0^1 (1-h)^s dh \int_0^1 (1-k)^s dk = \frac{1}{s+1} \frac{1}{s+1} = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \\ \text{Second term} &= \int_0^1 h^s dh \int_0^1 (1-k)^s dk = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \\ \text{Third term} &= \int_0^1 (1-h)^s dh \int_0^1 k^s dk = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \\ \text{Fourth term} &= \int_0^1 h^s dh \int_0^1 k^s dk = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \end{aligned}$$

then,

$$Q_{i,j}^q \leq \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \left[M_{i,j}^{(1,1)} + M_{i,j}^{(2,1)} + M_{i,j}^{(1,2)} + M_{i,j}^{(2,2)} \right]$$

Lets take the $\frac{1}{q}$ power

$$Q_{i,j}^q \leq \frac{1}{(s+1)^{2/q}} \left[\sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 M_{i,j} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q \right]^{1/q}$$

We calculated four terms. The same procedure is applied to remaining 12 terms. Lets call the outher sum of 16 terms Q

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left[\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_i, N_j) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_i, N_{j+1}) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_{i+1}, N_j) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_{i+1}, N_{j+1}) \right|^q \right]^{1/q} \tag{19}$$

For example: $i = 2, j = 2 \Rightarrow [M_2, M_3] x [N_2, N_3]$. We have,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_2, N_2) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_2, N_3) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_3, N_2) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_3, N_3) \right|^q \right]^{1/q} \\ (2, 2) &= \left[\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2} \right) \right|^q \right]^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

The remaining 12 terms use the formula,only the four derivative values in parentheses vary depending on which two consecutive interval corners on the X and Y axes they belong to. The proof is completed.

Corollary 4.1. Taking $s = 1$ in Theorem 4.2, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{144^2} \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p+1)} \right)^{2/p} \frac{1}{2^{2/q}} \\ & \quad \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i, i+1\}, \{j, j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_k, N_k) \right|^q \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 4.2. If we take the limit $p \rightarrow \infty$ (which implies $q = 1$) in Theorem 4.2. Meaning that $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|$ is coordinate s -convex, the following inequality is obtained. For $q = 1$ the coefficient $\frac{1}{(s+1)^{2/q}}$ simplies to $\frac{1}{(s+1)^2}$. L^p limit as $p \rightarrow \infty$, $\left(\frac{1+2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p+1)} \right)^{2/p} \rightarrow \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^2 = \frac{4}{9}$. Then we have,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \tag{20} \\ & \leq \frac{4(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{9 \cdot 144^2} \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i, i+1\}, \{j, j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_k, N_k) \right| \right) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.3. Let $B : [\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function such that the mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$ exists and is integrable on $[\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2]$. If $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q$ is (s_1, s_2) -convex in the second sense for some fixed $s_1, s_2 \in (0, 1]$ and $q \geq 1$, then the following inequality holds: **1)** The weighted sum $\sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j)$ uses the Bullen-Simpson weights $W=(1,4,2,4,1)$

$$\mathbf{2)} M_i \in \left\{ \mu_1, \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4}, \mu_2 \right\}, N_j \in \left\{ v_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2}, \frac{v_1 + 3v_2}{4}, v_2 \right\}$$

3) $C_{i,j}(s_1, s_2)$ are the resulting generalized coefficients, which for $i=1$ and $j=1$ (i.e. the term for $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu_1, v_1) \right|^q$)

Extreme points $(\mu_1, \mu_2) \rightarrow_{weights} (1, 1)$

Midpoints $\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4} \right) \rightarrow_{weights} (4, 2, 4)$

Four corners: Extreme points x extreme points

Six horizontal edge points: Midpoints x extreme points

Six vertical edge points: Extreme points x midpoints

Nine centers and quarterpoints: Midpoints x midpoints

The three point coefficient is the coefficient in front of $|B'(\mu_1)|^q$ and $|B'(\mu_2)|^q$

The midpoint coefficient is the total coefficient in front of the

$$\left| B' \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4} \right)^q \right|, \left| B' \left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2} \right)^q \right|, \left| B' \left(\frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4} \right)^q \right|$$

These coefficients;

$$\frac{4 \cdot 3^{s+1} \cdot s + 2 \cdot 3^{s+1} + 4}{5 \cdot 3^s (s+1)(s+2)} \text{ and } \frac{2 \cdot 3^{s+1} \cdot s - 2 \cdot 3^{s+1} + 2^{s+4}}{5 \cdot 3^s (s+1)(s+2)}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K(t, h) \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu_t, v_h) dt dh \right| \end{aligned}$$

where $K(t, h)$ is the kernel function and (μ_t, v_h) represent the coordinate wise linear combination points. Applying the properties of modulus and the Power-mean inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ &= \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 |K(t, h)|^p dt dh \right)^{1/p} \left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} |(\mu_t, v_h)|^q dt dh \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

The first factor involves the integration of the kernels p -norm. By the properties of Bullen-Simpson kernel this, simplifies to the product of two single kernel integrals

$$\left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 |K(t, h)|^p dt dh \right)^{1/p} = \left(\frac{5}{18} \right)^{1-1/q} \left(\frac{5}{18} \right)^{1-1/q} = \left(\frac{5}{18} \right)^{2(1-1/q)}$$

we focus on the second factor $\int_0^1 \int_0^1 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} |(\mu_t, v_h)|^q dt dh$. Since $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q$ is coordinate (s_1, s_2) convex, we apply the convexity property on each of the $5 \times 5 = 25$ subrectangles derived from the integral representation. For each term, the integral over the subrectangle (in the (μ, v)) plane is bounded by:

$$\left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} |(\mu_t, v_h)|^q dt dh \right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 \left(\frac{K_i(s_1)}{5.3^{s_1} \dots} \right) \left(\frac{K_j(s_2)}{5.3^{s_2} \dots} \right) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial \mu \partial v} (\mu_i, v_j)^q \right|$$

Substituting the results, we obtain the required inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \left(\frac{5}{18} \right)^{2(1-\frac{1}{q})} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 \left(C_{i,j}(s_1, s_2) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} (\mu_i, v_j) \right|^q \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

The proof is completed.

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